

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

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The book is part of the series “Open Publications for Society”,
an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

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DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

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SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniaili
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathaniaili, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

THE DIGITAL EMPLOYMENT GAP IN ALBANIA

Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education

Gertjana **HASALLA**

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Abstract

Albania faces a growing digital employment gap, marked by a mismatch between the skills required by the labour market and those provided by higher education. National initiatives such as e-Albania 2.0, GovTech Accelerator, SmartLabs, and DIGJIKOMP-AL have advanced digitalization, yet graduates often lack the applied competences expected in diverse sectors. This paper examines national strategies and institutional projects, including AKSHI–University partnerships, to assess current progress and persistent shortcomings. The research draws on policy reviews, institutional agreements, labour market surveys, and sectoral reports. Findings reveal limited integration of field-specific digital skills across curricula, regional and socioeconomic disparities in access to infrastructure, and insufficient industry–university collaboration. The study argues that systemic reform is required, moving from isolated ICT courses toward embedded digital competences in all disciplines, supported by professional development for faculty and targeted inclusion policies. Five recommendations are proposed: integrate digital learning outcomes across all programmes, expand faculty training in digital pedagogy, strengthen university–industry partnerships, address digital exclusion for underserved students, and establish continuous monitoring aligned with EU DigComp standards. Coordinated action between the Ministry of Education, AKSHI, universities, and the private sector, supported by EU cooperation, is essential to prepare graduates for a rapidly evolving digital economy.

Keywords: digital employment gap, higher education, Albania, digital inclusion, curriculum reform, labour market, digital skills

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

GERTJANA HASALLA

Gertjana Hasalla holds a Master of Science in Translation and Interpreting Studies and a Bachelor's in English Language and Literature, and she is currently pursuing a second Master's in Team Management & Leadership. With more than ten years of professional experience, she has built a strong career in program management, policy development and advocacy within the non-profit sector. She is Program Manager at the Centre for Labor Rights, where she leads program strategy, research and donor reporting, and has contributed to key publications on labor trends and social rights. In addition, she works as Policy and Project Expert at the Albanian Center for Population and Development, authoring strategic documents and proposals that support institutional development. Previously, she also coordinated multi-year projects on gender equality and community development with the Woman Forum Elbasan, while also teaching English for Specific Purposes at the University "Aleksander Xhuvani" of Elbasan. Internationally, Gertjana has participated in the U.S. State Department's Professional Fellows Program and the International Visitor Leadership Program. She has authored and co-authored several publications on migration governance, social rights, labor issues and gender budgeting, combining academic expertise with practical experience to advance equality and social justice.

INTRODUCTION AND AIMS OF THE STUDY

This study investigates the role of higher education in addressing Albania's digital employment gap. Its purpose is to explore how universities can align curricula with labour market needs, integrate digital competences across disciplines and reduce disparities in access. The research is designed to contribute both to national policy debates and international scholarship on digital transformation in education. Specifically, it aims to answer three questions:

- How are national strategies addressing digital competences in higher education?
- What structural and institutional barriers persist in aligning higher education with labour market requirements?
- What reforms are necessary to reduce the digital employment gap?

This research draws on the EU DigComp 2.2 framework (Carretero *et al.*, 2022), which identifies five dimensions of digital competence: information literacy, communication, content creation, safety and problem solving. The study also incorporates theories of digital inclusion and higher education reform, particularly those that emphasise the embedding of digital skills across disciplines rather than treating them as stand-alone ICT modules. The conceptual framework combines these theories with labour market alignment approaches that stress university–industry cooperation as a foundation for employability.

METHODOLOGY

The paper adopts a qualitative research design based on document analysis. Data were collected from policy reports, national strategies, EU frameworks, institutional agreements and labour market surveys. The selection of sources reflects both government and independent perspectives to ensure triangulation. Reliability was strengthened by cross-referencing findings with multiple reports from different institutions, while validity was ensured by grounding the analysis in the DigComp framework. The methodological approach is policy-driven but supported by conceptual models of digital competence and higher education transformation.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Although the study relies on secondary data, ethical considerations remain relevant. Potential bias in official policy documents, unequal representation of vulnerable groups and limitations of survey coverage are acknowledged. By highlighting these issues, the research aims to ensure responsible interpretation and to promote policies that address digital exclusion among disadvantaged populations.

CONTEXT: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN ALBANIA & LABOUR MARKET SHIFTS

Albania is undergoing a rapid digital transformation driven by public initiatives that aim to modernize public administration and the private sector in response to shifting employment needs. Among these, e-Albania 2.0 and the Digital Agenda 2022–2026 are central projects

shaping this transformation (University of Tirana, 2022). The Digital Agenda 2022–2026, prepared by the National Agency for Information Society, serves as a strategic roadmap for Albania’s transition to a digital society. It builds on earlier achievements, with the e-Albania platform now providing more than 95 percent of public services online, reducing bureaucracy, increasing transparency and streamlining administrative processes (AKSHI, 2023; DigWatch, 2022). The updated agenda outlines a vision for fully digitalized governance, enabling citizens and businesses to access services through integrated platforms supported by technologies such as artificial intelligence and block chain (DigWatch, 2022). E-Albania 2.0 is being designed around life-event-based services such as job seeking, retirement, and business registration, incorporating user-friendly interfaces, voice assistants, and accessibility enhancements (Monitor, 2024; University of Tirana, 2024).

The World Bank’s GovTech for Results programme, launched in 2023, has strengthened the reach of e-Albania 2.0 and set higher standards for inclusion. It reports a 40 percent increase in service applications via the platform and estimates that by 2029 nearly three million users will benefit from faster services and enhanced infrastructure (World Bank, 2025). In education, 216 SmartLabs have been established in primary schools, improving ICT access for approximately 35 000 students and providing training for more than 1 000 teachers and school leaders (World Bank, 2025). Additionally, vocational and innovation centres are being developed to equip young people with skills aligned with the evolving labour market (Ministry of State for Entrepreneurship and Business Climate, 2024).

The government has also invested significantly in the innovation ecosystem. The Smart Specialisation Strategy is supported by nearly €1.18 billion, with €14.5 million allocated for startups and SMEs, and more than €7 million granted over the past two years to strengthen innovative enterprises (Ministry of State for Entrepreneurship and Business Climate, 2024). Partnerships between the Albanian Cybernetics Association and Italian NGO NAMEX have strengthened the country’s internet infrastructure through the ANIX Internet Exchange Point, reducing access costs and improving connectivity (Balkan Insight, 2023).

Despite these improvements, gaps remain. Around 14 % of Albanians still lack internet access, particularly in rural and disadvantaged areas. Only about 4 % of the population possesses advanced digital skills, placing Albania behind other Western Balkan countries (Balkan Insight, 2023; DigWatch, 2022). Private sector demand for digital competences is rising quickly. Sectors such as banking, tourism, telecommunications, architecture, and media now require workers with expertise in cloud computing, data analysis, and sector-specific software, as well as the ability to adapt to technology-driven work environments (INSTAT, 2024; Ministry of Finance and Economy, 2022). The Employment and Skills Strategy 2022–2030 identifies persistent gaps between formal education and the practical skills employers require. It calls for integrating digital competences at all levels of education and aligning curricula more closely with labour market needs (Ministry of Finance and Economy, 2022). Surveys conducted by the European Training Foundation confirm that many Albanian graduates lack basic digital skills, including cloud technologies, data processing, and professional online communication, which limits their competitiveness in

digitized sectors (ETF, 2023). The Digital Agriculture and Rural Transformation (DART) program, launched in 2024 by the United Nations in collaboration with FAO, ILO, and ITU, aims to modernize rural services and agricultural practices. The initiative focuses on developing a national digital agriculture strategy aligned with EU standards, enhancing the Farmers' Portal, and providing training to farmers, students in technical schools, and public officials (United Nations Albania, 2024).

Overall, Albania's digital transformation is reshaping both the public and private sectors. Governance is moving toward fully integrated digital services, education is being updated with modern technology, the economy is supported through innovation hubs, and rural sectors are being connected through specialized programs. However, infrastructure limitations, skills gaps, and regional disparities remain significant challenges. For higher education, this means a pressing need to embed digital competences across curricula, strengthen partnerships with industry, and ensure equitable access to learning opportunities for all students.

HIGHER EDUCATION'S CURRENT CAPACITY TO ADDRESS DIGITAL NEEDS

Albanian universities have made notable advances in embracing digital education, particularly as a direct response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Many public institutions integrated Learning Management Systems and digital assessment tools into their workflows; these changes helped sustain teaching and learning. Nonetheless, efforts remain inconsistent and often limited to individual projects rather than system-wide transformation (Gugu & Kristo, 2023; MDPI, 2021). The abrupt shift to online learning during the pandemic exposed significant variability in readiness among universities. A survey conducted in early 2021 revealed that many institutions lacked strategic planning and infrastructure to support remote teaching. Faculty resorted to independent solutions, creating e-materials with minimal guidance; platforms such as Zoom and Google Classroom were adopted rapidly, sometimes without formal training or institutional backing (MDPI, 2021). These stop-gap measures enabled continuity in instruction, yet underscored the fragility of digital capabilities in higher education. A study examining lecturer and student experiences in the humanities at the University of Elbasan and the University of Tirana found that prior digital skills were generally inadequate; the traumatic shift catalysed skill development, but this occurred largely through self-directed learning rather than formal support. Despite progress, students' digital capabilities did not show substantial improvement beyond basic tool usage (Gugu & Kristo, 2023).

In 2021, AKSHI and the Ministry of Education launched the DIGJIKOMP-AL project to assess digital competences among academic staff in public higher education institutions (University of Tirana, 2022). Pilot self-assessments revealed uneven digital proficiency among faculty; some demonstrated adequate competencies, while others lacked training in digital pedagogy and emerging technologies. The project aimed to increase capacities to support quality teaching and learning; however, outcomes have not yet translated into scaled faculty development or widespread curriculum integration (University of Tirana, 2022).

Curriculum reform efforts emerged under the U2SID Erasmus+ project, aimed at embedding digital learning outcomes across higher education programmes. Universities including the University of Tirana, Polytechnic University of Tirana and University of Elbasan participated in workshops organized under the U2SID Digital Literacies Accelerator Program, which focuses on developing digital competences through collaborative and inclusive strategies (QSKN, 2023). A workshop held at the Mediterranean University of Albania in March 2024 emphasized integrating digital literacy across programmes, facilitating engagement between faculty, students and industry professionals, and modernizing study design (QSKN, 2024). These initiatives proposed integrating digital literacies across disciplines, enhancing teaching methods, and aligning programs with labour market needs. Yet, implementation remains limited to pilot activities, and many programmes still treat digital skills as isolated ICT modules rather than embedding them throughout curricula.

Some private universities made early strides in digital course offerings. Institutions such as Epoka University and Metropolitan University of Tirana, UMT introduced digitally oriented courses, leveraging their autonomy to innovate curricula. Epoka University offers programs in Computer Engineering, Business Administration and Architecture, where digital tools are naturally embedded (Epoka, 2025). These universities tend to operate with more agility and may incorporate digital components more readily; however, coordination with national standards and public sector reforms remains limited. Other universities developed in-house digital systems to manage academic workflows and support online teaching. For example, at the University of Shkodra “Luigj Gurakuqi”, the SMAK platform manages pedagogical loads and communications, while a Moodle-based system supports course delivery. This institution also launched a Continuing Education Training Laboratory to build lecturer skills in digital tools and online course design ((Demaj *et al.*, 2020). University of Elbasan deployed Moodle for specific departments, initially offering online teaching in social sciences with as many as 200 students participating. The university’s Educational Management System supports administrative functions, while the E-Learning platform is still limited to partial adoption. Only a negligible fraction of courses was designed as blended learning, and most remain entirely face-to-face (Ibid).

Despite these efforts, several challenges remain. A lack of coherent strategy means many *initiatives are project-based, time-limited and not institutionalized*. The breadth of digital integration varies widely across universities and per faculty. Most programmes still treat digital education as optional modules rather than intrinsic to all disciplines. Faculty development remains uneven; while some institutions invested in training and mentoring, many rely on self-learning and peer sharing. Students may develop familiarity with basic tools, but deeper digital skills such as data literacy, digital content creation or pedagogical technology integration remain uncommon. Moreover, private university innovations are rarely synchronized with national priorities. Public universities often lack the agility to implement reforms comprehensively, while private institutions may fail to contribute to public digital education transformation.

The pandemic highlighted the necessity of resilient digital infrastructure and digital

pedagogy. The DIGJIKOMP-AL and U2SID initiatives offer valuable inroads into institutionalizing digital competences, yet without system-wide adoption, their impact remains limited. Embedding digital skills across curricula requires professional development for academic staff, not just one-off trainings, but ongoing support for digital pedagogy in all disciplines. University governance structures should ensure digital literacies are integral to programmes objectives rather than add-on modules. Collaboration among public and private universities, alignment with national digital agendas and coordination with quality assurance mechanisms like ASCAL can help foster consistency. Shared platforms, resource centers and faculty networks may enable scaling of good practice.

Albanian universities responded to the pandemic by adopting digital tools and platforms under pressure. While progress was achieved in some areas, digital education remains fragmented. Pilot programmes such as DIGJIKOMP-AL and U2SID offer practical frameworks for embedding digital literacies, yet need scaling and integration with institutional mandates. Private universities provide examples of innovation, though alignment with broader educational transformation is weak.

For sustainable change, higher education institutions must move from reactive digital adoption towards strategic integration. This means equipping faculty in digital pedagogy, redesigning curricula to include digital competences across all programmes, and aligning efforts across public and private sectors. The digital transformation of university education will remain nascent until challenges of coordination, capacity and policy are addressed.

THE MISSING LINK: ALIGNING UNIVERSITIES WITH THE LABOR MARKET

Despite growing recognition of the digital employment gap, structural misalignments persist. Employers report that graduates are not adequately prepared for real-world digital tasks, especially in fields like engineering, health sciences, public administration, journalism (RisiAlbania, 2024) and education (Nathanaili, 2023). For instance, engineering students may receive strong theoretical training but minimal exposure to simulation software or data platforms widely used in the industry. A critical reason for this gap is the limited communication between universities and employers. Career offices, where available, tend to focus on traditional placement services such as job listings rather than developing active, skills-based partnerships with businesses (RisiAlbania, n.d.). These services seldom engage in joint curriculum design, workplace retraining modules or shared internships aligned with digital competencies.

There are promising but fragmented efforts to bridge this gap. In 2023, the National Agency for Information Society (AKSHI) entered an agreement with the University of Tirana aimed at involving students in digital public service development (AKSHI, 2023). This initiative created opportunities for students to work on real digital platforms, which could help them understand practical public-sector needs. However, such collaborations are rare and system-wide frameworks to scale them across universities do not yet exist. Another major issue is the absence of system-wide monitoring mechanisms that ensure academic

content stays aligned with labour market trends. There is no mandatory requirement for universities to benchmark their curricula against established EU digital competence frameworks such as DigComp 2.2 (Carretero *et al.*, 2022). Without these benchmarks, academic programmes may fall behind rapidly evolving professional expectations. Moreover, comprehensive data on graduate employability, especially concerning digital readiness, remains limited. Universities do not routinely track employment outcomes by field or digital competence levels. Without reliable statistics, policymakers and institutions lack evidence needed for targeted and effective reform.

Some progress has been made through projects like RisiAlbania, supported by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation and implemented by Helvetas and Partners Albania (RisiAlbania, n.d.-a). This project works to improve career guidance and job intermediation services, especially in sectors such as ICT. It helps to establish Skills Sectoral Committees that bring together businesses, educational institutions, and policymakers to reflect changing professional skills needs (RisiAlbania, n.d.-a). Such committees could serve as future platforms for university-industry collaboration if expanded. Despite this, RisiAlbania's initiatives are somewhat external to university systems and do not fully embed digital competency alignment into academic governance. Their work is impactful, yet not integrated into mainstream university processes.

The misalignment between university curricula and employer needs has tangible consequences. Graduates frequently require additional on-the-job training to become productive, increasing hiring costs and delaying full performance. In sectors like journalism and public administration, this means students may graduate with outdated skills that do not match current digital workflows or platforms. This misalignment also contributes to brain drain. Young professionals, finding limited opportunities in local markets, often emigrate to countries where their digital skills are more valued or better matched. This exacerbates the challenge for both universities and the economy (RisiAlbania, n.d.-a).

To close this gap, several actions are essential:

- Establish formal benchmarking frameworks that require universities to map their programmes against EU digital competence frameworks like DigComp 2.2. This would ensure curricula evolve with industry needs (Carretero *et al.*, 2022).
- Institutionalize collaboration between universities and businesses through internships, pilot projects and joint course design. Platforms similar to RisiAlbania's sectoral committees could be embedded in academic governance to guide program development.
- Empower career centers to go beyond placement services by organizing industry-led digital skilling events, fostering alumni mentorships and co-designing assessments aligned with workplace requirements.
- Gather and publish graduate data on employment outcomes, digital readiness, and field-specific performance. Robust data would inform curriculum reform and signal where education risks falling behind market needs.
- Scale AKSHI-university partnerships like the one with the University of Tirana by replicating digital public service co-development projects across disciplines and campuses.

REGIONAL & SOCIO-ECONOMIC BARRIERS TO DIGITAL INCLUSION

Digital exclusion remains a defining barrier for many Albanian students. Those from rural areas and low-income households face a combination of poor broadband access, limited exposure to digital tools in earlier education, and minimal support for acquiring advanced skills. Even though pre-university digital education programs such as SmartLabs have reached numerous schools, the divide in tertiary institutions is both glaring and persistent (UNICEF Albania, 2023). Students in rural areas often endure unstable or limited Internet connectivity. While mobile coverage may exist, fixed-line broadband is scarce and costly. In 2022, only about 9 % of rural residents had fixed-line connections, compared to 31 % in urban areas (AKEP, 2024). This disparity means that students outside major cities frequently lack reliable access to online learning platforms or digital resources.

Infrastructure gaps persist despite national efforts. The National Plan for Sustainable Digital Infrastructure (2020–2025) targeted universal broadband and improved connectivity for schools and institutions by 2025. Yet implementation in rural parts has lagged due to funding gaps, regulatory complexity, and a focus on profitable urban regions (DigWatch, 2020). Without broadband at home or institution, rural students face barriers in participating in digital learning or demonstrating digital competence.

Efforts such as SmartLabs and the Albania Digital Education Project focus on equipping primary and secondary schools with ICT infrastructure and teachers with digital pedagogy training. The initiative aimed to establish over 600 SmartLabs benefiting roughly 150,000 students, particularly in remote areas (UNESCO, 2021). Yet the impact in secondary and tertiary education remains limited, and inequalities continue to influence digital skill acquisition. In many rural schools, infrastructure and connectivity are still lacking. In one remote village, only 46 percent of schools (primary and secondary) had any Internet access and a mere 5.3 percent had Wi-Fi (BIRN, 2025). Teachers struggle to conduct even basic digital lessons, often relying on personal devices. These disparities in foundational digital exposure feed into higher education, where students from such backgrounds may enter under-prepared.

Public universities in peripheral regions consistently have weaker digital infrastructure compared to their peers in Tirana. Students and faculty in these universities face challenges accessing reliable Wi-Fi, up-to-date laboratory equipment, and modern educational platforms. These gaps limit both teaching quality and students' ability to develop advanced digital skills. Moreover, faculty at under-resourced universities often lack access to training in digital pedagogy or emerging technologies. Without structured internal capacity building, lecturers continue to teach using traditional methods, maintaining the digital gap across student cohorts.

Graduates from under-resourced universities face direct consequences in the job market. They are less likely to be considered for roles in digitalized sectors such as IT, finance, media or public administration, where digital fluency and familiarity with platforms are essential. Competing against peers from better-equipped institutions, these graduates often experience

lower employability and increased vulnerability to unemployment or underemployment. Disparities in digital readiness also perpetuate socioeconomic inequalities. Students from rural or low-income backgrounds frequently have fewer opportunities to access internships, industry alignments, or networking events that could offset their digital skills deficit.

Various efforts aim to reverse this trend, though many remain pilot projects. Mobile labs and regional development programs, including portions of the DART (Digital Agriculture and Rural Transformation) initiative, deliver digital training to rural youth, farmers, and vocational school students (ILO, 2024). These programmes build digital capabilities related to agriculture, but their reach is often limited in scope and duration. Similarly, the Digital Agriculture for Rural Transformation (DART), led by FAO, ILO, and ITU, focuses mainly on extending digital agricultural knowledge through platforms like the Farmers' Portal (UN, 2025). These tools may not directly address digital exclusion among university students. While they build rural digital access in one sector, broader, systemic solutions are still needed across education levels. Many digital inclusion initiatives depend on limited donor funding or single-phase grants. Once the initial project ends, maintenance, infrastructure upgrades and scaling efforts often stall. Without sustainable financing and institutionalization, these efforts risk remaining fragmented and short-lived. The lack of local ownership also restricts longevity. Projects led by external partners may not embed training or infrastructure into the university governance system. Once the project team withdraws, the benefits may fade without internal champions or long-term planning.

Closing the gap: suggestions for lasting impact

Closing the digital exclusion gap requires holistic and sustainable policies:

- Expand broadband access through public-private partnerships, universal service funds, and infrastructure mapping to ensure connectivity for all universities, hospitals, schools, and homes (DigWatch, 2020).
- Institutionalize SmartLabs in tertiary institutions, particularly in under-resourced regions, with ongoing technical and pedagogical support rather than one-off deployments.
- Offer dedicated funding for university digital infrastructure and faculty training in peripheral universities to level the playing field with institutions in major cities.
- Use data-driven strategies to map student digital readiness and infrastructure gaps. This ensures targeted investment in the most impacted areas.
- Integrate digital literacy into core tertiary curricula across disciplines and promote inclusive access, online libraries, coding tools, simulation platforms that bridges regional divides.
- Create sustainable models, like revolving funds or local co-financing, to ensure infrastructure maintenance and avoid pilot attrition.

Digital exclusion rooted in geography and socioeconomic background deepens the employment gap by limiting students' development of essential digital skills. Pre-university interventions such as SmartLabs testify to potential, yet inequalities persist into tertiary

education. Rural institutions lag behind, and digital readiness varies significantly across regions. While some mobile labs and sector-specific programmes offer temporary relief, their reach is narrow and uncertain in longevity. To close the employment gap, Albania must prioritize equitable digital infrastructure and literacy investments that are strategic, inclusive, and enduring.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To address the digital employment gap, a systemic transformation is required in how Albanian universities understand, teach and assess digital competences. This paper proposes five key strategies:

- **Integrate Digital Learning Outcomes Across All Disciplines:** Move beyond ICT courses and embed relevant digital competences in every academic program.
- **Expand Professional Development for Faculty:** Provide continuous training in digital pedagogy and sector-specific digital tools.
- **Build Stronger University–Industry Linkages:** Develop joint projects, digital internships and mentorships that mirror market conditions.
- **Target Digital Exclusion:** Create inclusive policies that support students from underserved regions and backgrounds with digital access and learning support.
- **Establish Monitoring Mechanisms:** Regularly assess digital competence integration and labour market responsiveness using frameworks such as DigComp.

These actions require joint coordination between the Ministry of Education, AKSHI, universities and the private sector, supported by EU cooperation and local policy reforms. Without such alignment, Albania risks falling further behind in regional digital competitiveness.

CONCLUSIONS

Albania's higher education system is at a turning point. Digitalisation has advanced significantly at the national level, yet universities remain fragmented in their response. The findings demonstrate that despite national efforts, higher education continues to treat digital skills as optional rather than fundamental. There are significant gaps in faculty training, weak integration of competences across curricula and limited alignment with market expectations. Regional and socioeconomic disparities further deepen exclusion, leaving many students disadvantaged. University–industry cooperation remains fragmented, with few institutionalised mechanisms for embedding workplace skills into academic programmes. The study shows that without systematic reform, Albanian graduates will remain unprepared for the digital labour market.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Model of the Digital Employment Gap and Proposed Reforms

Embedding digital competences, expanding faculty development and ensuring equitable access are necessary steps to reduce the digital employment gap. The study underscores the importance of systemic reform, coordinated action and continuous monitoring to prepare graduates for the future of work. The Fig. 1 illustrates the relationship between national strategies, higher education institutions, labour market demands and the proposed reforms.

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

PROF. ILIA NINKA

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education is about more than technology. It is about developing university-level strategies and adequate national and regional policies to support digital transformation. Albanian Higher Education Institutions have not yet developed an ethical framework for the use of ChatGPT and similar AI applications.

DR. VALBONA NATHANAILI

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

DR. KETI HOXHA

Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

PROF. DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIC

... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

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